

Comparison of diagnostic performances of HDV-RNA quantification assays used in clinical practice: Results from a national quality control multicenter study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A reliable quantification of hepatitis D virus (HDV) RNA is of paramount importance for monitoring patients under antiviral therapy. This quality control study compares the diagnostic performances of quantitative HDV-RNA assays used in clinical practice.

Methods: Two HDV-RNA sample panels were quantified in 30 centers by RoboGene (N = 9 laboratories), EurobioPlex (N = 7), RealStar (N = 4), AltoStar (N = 1), Bosphore (N = 3), Bosphore-on-InGenius (N = 1), Dia. Pro (N = 2), Nuclear-Laser-Medicine (N = 1) and 3 in-house assays. Panel A and B comprised 8 serial dilutions of WHO/HDV standard (range: 0.5–5.0 log₁₀ IU/ml) and 20 clinical samples (range: 0.5–6.0 log₁₀ IU/ml), respectively. The following parameters were determined: sensitivity by 95 % LOD (limit of detection), precision by intra- and inter-run CV (coefficient of variation), accuracy by the differences between expected-observed HDV-RNA, linearity by linear regression analysis.

Results: 95 % LOD varied across assays and centers underlining heterogeneous sensitivities: AltoStar had the lowest 95 % LOD (3 IU/ml) followed by RealStar (10 [min–max: 3–316] IU/ml), Bosphore-on-InGenius (10 IU/ml), RoboGene (31 [3–316] IU/ml), Nuclear-Laser-Medicine (31 IU/ml) and EuroBioPlex (100 [100–316] IU/ml). Moreover, 6 assays (RoboGene, EurobioPlex, RealStar, AltoStar, Nuclear-Laser-Medicine and In-house) showed <0.5 log₁₀ IU/ml differences between expected and observed HDV-RNA for all dilutions while other assays had >1 log₁₀ IU/ml underestimations. RealStar, Bosphore-on-InGenius and EurobioPlex had the highest precision (mean intra-run CV < 20 %). Inter-run CV was higher for all assays, with CVs < 25 % for RealStar, AltoStar, Nuclear-Laser-Medicine and EurobioPlex. Seven assays (RoboGene/AltoStar/RealStar/EurobioPlex/Nuclear-Laser-Medicine/In-house) showed a good linearity (R² > 0.90), but for HDV-RNA < 1000 IU/ml only Bosphore-on-InGenius, AltoStar, RealStar and Robogene showed a R² > 0.85.

Conclusions: This study underlines heterogeneous sensitivities (inter- and intraassays), that could hamper proper HDV-RNA quantification, particularly at low viral loads. This raises the need to improve the diagnostic performance of most assays for properly identifying virological response to anti-HDV drugs.

1. Introduction

Hepatitis D virus (HDV) is a satellite virus that can infect hepatocytes only in presence of hepatitis B virus (HBV) [1] exploiting the HBV surface proteins (HBsAg) for the release of its progeny and de novo entry into hepatocytes [1]. HBV + HDV infection causes the most severe viral hepatitis, leading to cirrhosis in 70 % of cases within 10 years [2].

A proper HDV diagnosis relies on the detection of anti-HDV

antibodies and on the determination of active viral replication by quantifying serum HDV-RNA, thus defining the status of chronic HDV infection [3,4]. Active viral replication plays a pivotal role in triggering liver inflammation and in turn liver disease progression, including HCC onset [5–7].

The quantification of HDV-RNA is also critical for monitoring virological response to anti-HDV treatment [4]. Bulevirtide is the first approved drug for the treatment of HBV/HDV-coinfected patients in Europe, is an entry inhibitor that targets the sodium-taurocholate-co-transporting polypeptide receptor and avoiding the entry of HDV and HBV virions into hepatocytes [4].

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For a long time, HDV-RNA quantification relied on non-standardized home-made assays. The introduction of bulevirtide has prompted the development of commercial assays characterized by different analytical performances as emerged in preliminary inter-laboratory studies [8,9].

In this light, this study is one of the largest quality assurance programs, involving 30 virological centers throughout Italy, aimed at finely assessing and comparing the diagnostic performances of the currently available assays used in clinical practise for HDV-RNA quantification.

2. Methods

2.1. Participating centers

This multicenter study included 30 reference virological centers in Italy, participating in the Vironet C Italian network (<https://www.vironetc.org/>), that were originally asked to participate based on the use of assays for HDV-RNA quantification in routine clinical practice (Fig. S1).

Table 1 reports the main characteristics of the assays used by centers. For each assay, sample equivalent was calculated according to the formula:

$(\text{serum volume}) \times (\text{RNA volume in amplification}) / (\text{eluate volume obtained after extraction})$. The closer the sample equivalent is to the initial volume of the sample, the higher the sensitivity of the assay is.

2.2. Quality control panels

Two quality control panels (Panel A and B) were assembled by the coordinating center (University of Rome Tor Vergata) and sent to each participating laboratory for blind testing, using the methodology routinely used at each center. Panel A and B samples were shipped by using a courier specialized in the management of infectious material. Shipping was organized within 1 week after the preparation of Panel A and B. In particular, 3 expeditions were set up simultaneously towards the Centers in Northern, Central and Southern Italy each. Samples were

shipped in UN3373 compliant boxes at controlled temperature in dry ice at -80°C and were delivered within 1 day of picking up the samples at the Coordinating Center. Temperature stability during transport was verified using a data logger endowed by an alarm status and transport temperature graph. By visualizing data logger reports, the temperature was steady at $-80 \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ in each expedition.

Panel A was composed of 8 serial dilutions of the “WHO HDV International Standard” (PEI 7657/12, provided by Paul Ehrlich Institute) ranging from $5.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml to $0.5 \log_{10}$ IU/ml (3 IU/ml). A $0.5 \log_{10}$ serial dilution was applied for HDV-RNA concentrations $\leq 3.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml for a better definition of assay sensitivity.

Each center received 1 tube for the concentrations of 5.0 and $4.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml and 3 tubes for the concentrations of 3.0, 2.5, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, $0.5 \log_{10}$ IU/ml, for a total of 20 tubes each containing 500 μl of sample. Nucleic acids extraction was carried out from each tube and HDV-RNA was quantified in triplicate from each extraction. On this basis, 3 measurements were available for concentrations of 5.0 and $4.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml and 9 for concentrations $\leq 3.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml.

The WHO HDV-RNA standard was provided lyophilized, with a concentration of 575,000 IU/ml. All the dilutions were prepared by using serum screened negative to HBV, HDV, HCV and HIV markers.

In order to evaluate a potential loss of biological activity of the International Standard, Centers were stratified according to the lag-time between the delivery of samples and their processing at each participating Center. Panel A samples were processed after a median (IQR) time of 2.3 (2.1–2.5) months. 7 Centers have processed samples within 2 months, 20 between 2 and 3 months and 4 after 3 months. In each group of Centers, we determined for each serial dilution of the International Standard, the difference between the observed and expected concentration of HDV-RNA. By applying Spearman test, a complete lack of correlation was observed between such differences and the lag-time ($\text{Rho} = -0.02$, $\text{P} = 0.92$). In particular, the differences between the observed and expected values ranged from -0.1 to -0.6 for the group of Centers that have processed samples in <2 months, from 0 to -0.4 for the group of Centers that have processed samples between 2 and 3

Table 1
Characteristics of the assays for HDV-RNA quantification.

Assay and company	No. of centers ^a	Nucleic acids extraction method	Serum volume (μl)	Elution volume ^b (μl)	RNA volume ^c (μl)	Sample volume equivalent ^d (μl)
RoboGene HDV-RNA Quantification Kit 2.0 <i>Roboscreen, LOD 6 IU/ml</i>	9	RoboScreen INSTANT Virus RNA/DNA Kit (N = 7) ^e	400	60	5	33.3
		Qiagen EZ1 (N = 2)	400	60	5	33.3
EurobioPlex HDV qRT-PCR 004 <i>EurobioScientific, LOD 100 IU/ml</i>	7	ELITech ELITE InGenius (N = 6) ^f	500	50	10	100.0
		Qiagen QIA Symphony (N = 1)	400	60	10	66.7
RealStar® HDV RT-PCR Kit 1.0 <i>Altona, LOD 9.5 IU/ml</i>	4	ELITech ELITE InGenius (N = 2) ^g	500	100	25	125.0
		Biomerieux EasyMAG (N = 1)	500	50	25	250.0
		Qiagen QIAamp Viral RNA (N = 1) ^e	200	50	25	100.0
AltoStar® HDV RT-PCR Kit 1.5 <i>Altona, LOD 3 IU/ml</i>	1	Altona AltoStar AM16 (N = 1) ^f	500	60	45	375.0
Bosphore HDV Real-Time PCR Kit <i>Anatolia Geneworks, LOD 12 IU/ml</i>	4	ELITech ELITE InGenius (N = 1)	200	100	10	20.0
		ELITech ELITE InGenius (N = 1) ^f	600	50	10	120.0
		Qiagen QIAcube (N = 1)	200	60	10	33.3
		Qiagen QIA Symphony (N = 1)	500	140	10	35.7
HDV Quantitation Real-Time PCR kit <i>Dia.Pro Diagnostic Bioprobes, LOD 250 IU/ml</i>	2	Biomerieux EasyMAG (N = 1) ^g	500	25	10	200.0
		Qiagen QIAamp Viral RNA (N = 1) ^e	140	50	10	28.0
HDV Real TM Quant <i>Nuclear Laser Medicine, LOD 30 IU/ml</i>	1	ELITech ELITE InGenius (N = 1)	200	100	12.5	25.0
Home Made ddPCR or Real-Time PCR	3	Qiagen EZ1 (N = 1)	400	60	5	33.3
		Roche MagNA Pure 24 (N = 1)	200	50	5	20.0
		Qiagen QIA Symphony (N = 1)	400	90	5	22.2

^a One center has tested two different assays: RoboGene and Bosphore on ELITech InGenius.

^b The volume of eluate obtained after nucleic acid extraction.

^c The RNA volume indicates the volume of the eluate used for HDV-RNA quantification.

^d This parameter reflects the amount of original serum sample actually tested in PCR for HDV-RNA quantification.

^e Manual nucleic acid extraction method.

^f Fully automated system, allowing extraction and sequential amplification in the same instrument. LOD 5 IU/ml.

^g Extraction method not validated for the assay.

months and from 0.1 to 0.2 for the group of Centers that have processed samples in >3 months.

Panel B was composed of 20 tubes, divided as: 17 containing a wide range of HDV-RNA concentrations (6.7–6.0–5.5–5.0–4.3–3.7–3.5–3.0–2.6–2.3–2.0–1.6–1.3–1.0–0.9–0.8–0.5 log₁₀ IU/ml). These concentrations were obtained by diluting residual samples of 9 anonymized chronically HDV genotype 1 infected patients with known HDV-RNA measurement assessed by RoboGene HDV-RNA Quantification Kit 2.0. The RoboGene assay was considered as reference for the quantification of Panel B samples since it is endowed by the highest declared sensitivity and was the assay used in the clinical trials aimed at evaluating the efficacy of bulevirtide [10,11]. All the dilutions were prepared using the same diluent of panel A. Additionally, 3 tubes were used as negative controls obtained from residual serum from blood donors screened negative to HBV, HDV, HCV and HIV markers.

For panel B, nucleic acids extraction was carried out from each tube and HDV-RNA was quantified in quadruplicate or quintuplicate from each extraction (according to the volume of eluate required by the assays) in 3 independent runs.

Overall, each center received 40 tubes (20 for Panel A and 20 for Panel B) and performed at least 144 HDV-RNA quantifications for a total of 4280 HDV-RNA quantifications analysed.

Overall, the time between the preparation of the samples at the coordinating Center up to the completion of samples' processing by all Centers was 2.6 (2.4–2.8) months.

The Center using Altona AltoStar received an increased volume of samples due to the amount of eluate needed for each RT-PCR: 45 µl out of the 60 µl of eluate obtained by nucleic acids extraction.

The unit of measurement was IU/ml for most assays, with the exception of Bosphore, Nuclear laser medicine and Home-made assays. For these assays, the HDV-RNA value expressed in copies/ml was multiplied by the conversion factor of 0.12, 0.97 and 0.97, respectively in order to obtain the corresponding IU/ml in according with the manufacturer instructions or [12].

HDV-RNA was considered negative (or undetectable) if the result was lower than the lower limit of detection (LOD) declared by the respective assay, while HDV-RNA was considered "positive unquantifiable" (or detectable) if the result was lower than the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) declared by the respective assay.

2.3. Parameters used for assessing the diagnostic performances of the assays for HDV-RNA quantification

All the HDV-RNA quantifications were used to assess the following parameters (Table 2):

- Sensitivity was determined by calculating the 95 % limit of detection (95 % LOD) defined as the lowest HDV-RNA load detected in at least 95 % of replicates. 95 % LOD was determined for each participating center and assessed considering only the HDV-RNA concentrations of panel A <1000 IU/ml.
 - Accuracy was determined by calculating the distance between the observed and the expected value of HDV-RNA. The observed value was expressed as the mean of HDV-RNA replicates obtained for a given dilution. The distance was calculated for each HDV-RNA concentration of panel A and for each participating center.
 - Precision was determined by calculating the intra- and inter-run coefficient of variation (CV). CV was calculated for each HDV-RNA concentration of panel B and for each participating center.
- The intra-run CV was calculated considering the HDV-RNA replicates obtained in a single run while inter-run CV was calculated considering the HDV-RNA values obtained in 3 independent runs.
- Linearity was determined for each assay by linear regression analysis using the observed and expected HDV-RNA values of both panel A and B. The observed value was defined as the mean of HDV-RNA

Table 2
Parameters for the evaluation of assays' performances.

Parameter	Sample panel	Replicates	Output
Sensitivity	A	3 replicates for 5.0 and 4.0 log ₁₀ (IU/ml) and 9 replicates for concentrations ranging from 3.0 to 0.5 log ₁₀ (IU/ml).	LOD 95 %, defined as the lowest HDV-RNA load detected in at least 95 % of replicates.
	A + B	All the replicates from panels A and B.	Percentage of qualitatively detected HDV-RNA replicates
Accuracy	A	3 replicates for 5.0 and 4.0 log ₁₀ (IU/ml) and 9 replicates for concentrations ranging from 3.0 to 0.5 log ₁₀ (IU/ml).	Mean difference between observed and expected values at each tested HDV-RNA load for each center.
Precision	B	5 replicates in three independent runs.	Intra- and inter-run coefficient of variation (CV)
Linearity	A + B	All the replicates from panels A and B.	R ² determined by linear regression analysis.

replicates obtained for a given dilution by all the centers using the same assay. In order to exclude a potential bias attributed to the use of the RoboGene as reference assay, the analysis was repeated only on Panel A samples.

- Rate of qualitative detection was determined for each assay and for each expected HDV-RNA concentration of panel B <3 log₁₀ IU/ml. The rate of detection was defined as the percentage of qualitatively detected HDV-RNA replicates.

2.4. Impact of the nucleic acid extraction methods on the assays' sensitivity

In order to more finely evaluate a potential impact of the extraction methods on the sensitivity of the assay, we calculated the median (IQR) difference between the observed 95 % LOD and the LOD declared by the assays according to:

- each nucleic acid extraction method (Table S1);
- each combination of nucleic acid extraction method and Real-Time PCR assay (Table S2).

The extraction platforms by Qiagen were evaluated singly and grouped according to beads- or silica-based methods. Statistically significant differences were assessed by Mann–Whitney test.

3. Results

3.1. Assays used for HDV-RNA quantification

The main features of the assays used at the 30 participating centers are shown in Table 1. The RoboGene and EurobioPlex assays were the most frequently used (9 and 7 centers, respectively), followed by Altona kits (4 RealStar and 1 AltoStar version) and Bosphore (4 centers) (Table 1). Furthermore, the Dia.Pro assay was used by 2 centers, while Nuclear Laser Medicine assay by 1 center (Table 1). Finally, 3 centers have used home-made assays: 2 based on Real-Time PCR and 1 on droplet digital PCR (Table 1).

The main protocol parameters of assays were highly heterogeneous concerning nucleic acids extraction methods, real-time RT-PCR technologies, eluate volume and the volume of the eluate used for HDV-RNA quantification (Table 1). Fully automated systems, allowing extraction and sequential amplification in the same instrument were used by: EurobioPlex (N = 6 centers), AltoStar (N = 1) and Bosphore (N = 1)

assays (Table 1).

3.2. Assays' sensitivity

The lowest 95 % LODs were detected for AltoStar assay (3 IU/ml, albeit used by a single center), RealStar (median [min–max]: 10 [3–316] IU/ml), followed by RoboGene (31 [3–316] IU/ml) and Nuclear Laser Medicine assay (31 IU/ml) (Table 3). To note, the AltoStar assay, characterized by the lowest LOD 95 %, had the highest sample equivalent (373 μ l versus \leq 250 μ l for all other assays) (Table 1).

Higher median 95 % LODs were observed for EurobioPlex and Bosphore assays (median [min–max]: 100 [100–316] IU/ml and 174 [10–316] IU/ml, respectively) (Table 3).

Focusing on the Bosphore assay, two centers have used this assay with the ELITech nucleic acid extraction platform (Table 1) but applying two different sample equivalents (120 for one and 20 for the other). We note that the assay with a higher sample equivalent was characterized by a lower 95 % LOD (10 IU/ml and 31 IU/ml, respectively).

In the 2 centers with the Dia.Pro assay, the 95 % LODs were 316 and 1000 IU/ml (Table 3). Furthermore, for the home-made assays, the 95 % LOD ranged from 31 to 316 IU/ml (Table 3).

We then evaluated the impact of nucleic acids extraction methods on assays' sensitivity. In line with a previous study [13], the difference between the 95 % LOD and the LOD declared by RoboGene was lower when the manual nucleic acid extraction kit (RoboScreen INSTANT Virus RNA/DNA Kit) was used (Table S2).

Similarly, significantly lower differences between the 95 % LOD and the declared LOD were observed when the extraction platform by ELITech was used in combination with the RT-PCR assays by EuroBioplex, RealStar, Bosphore and Nuclear Laser Medicine (median difference [IQR]: 0.5 (0.0–3.0 for ELITech extraction method vs 45.5 [4.0–304.6] for the other extraction methods, P-value: 0.023).

Moreover, significantly lower differences between the 95 % LOD and the declared LOD were observed for the ELITech (N = 11) than the Qiagen extraction methods (N = 9) (median difference [IQR]: 0.5 (0.0–3.0 for ELITech extraction method vs 304 [95–309] for the Qiagen

Table 3
Sensitivity of the different assays.

Assay and company	Centers (N)	Limit of detection 95 % (95 % LOD) ^a	
		Median LOD 95 % (IU/ml) ^b	LOD 95 % Range MIN–MAX (IU/ml)
RoboGene HDV-RNA Quantification Kit 2.0 Roboscreen	9	31	3–316
EurobioPlex HDV qRT-PCR 004 EurobioScientific	7	100	100–316
RealStar® HDV RT-PCR Kit 1.0 Altona	4	10	3–316
AltoStar® HDV RT-PCR Kit 1.5 Altona	1	-	3
Bosphore HDV Real-Time PCR Kit Anatolia Geneworks	4	174	10 ^c –316
HDV Quantitation Real-Time PCR kit Dia.Pro Diagnostic Bioprobes	2	-	316–1000
HDV Real TM Quant Nuclear Laser Medicine	1	-	31
Home Made ddPCR or Real-Time PCR	3	-	31–316

^a The 95 % Limit of Detection (95 % LOD) was defined as the lowest HDV-RNA load detected in at least 95 % of replicates (N = 9).

^b For each assay, the median (min–max) 95 % LOD was calculated by using the 95 % LODs observed for each center.

^c 10 IU/ml was the 95 % LOD obtained for the Bosphore assay used on the Elitech InGenius instrument.

extraction methods, P-value: 0.039) (Tables S1 and S2).

No significant differences were observed between the beads- and the silica-based Qiagen method.

3.3. Accuracy and precision

Seven out nine assays showed a mean distance $<0.5 \log_{10}$ IU/ml between the observed and expected HDV-RNA values for all dilutions tested in Panel A (Fig. 1), highlighting good accuracy.

Focusing on the 5 commercial assays used by >2 Centers, we noted that for all the Centers using EurobioPlex and for most Centers using RoboGene (7 out of 9), the differences between the observed and the expected value were comparable across the different HDV-RNA concentrations and were all $<0.5 \log$ IU/ml, highlighting high accuracy. The results observed for EurobioPlex are also in line with the automation of the ELITech platform. Conversely, the remaining 2 Centers using Robogene were associated with $>1 \log$ underestimation or overestimation across the different HDV-RNA concentrations, respectively.

Similarly, for 3 out of the 4 Centers using RealStar, the differences between the observed and the expected value were comparable across the different HDV-RNA concentrations and were all $<\pm 0.5 \log$ IU/ml. Conversely, a single center was systematically associated with an underestimation ranging from -0.5 to -1.5 .

Only for 1 out of the 3 Centers using Bosphore, the differences between the observed and the expected value were $<0.5 \log$ IU/ml and were comparable across most HDV-RNA concentrations.

For the remaining 2 Centers using Bosphore and for the Centers using Dia.Pro, the differences between the observed and the expected value were remarkably higher than $+0.5 \log$ IU/ml.

By evaluating the precision, all the assays were characterized by a mean intra-run CV $< 25 \%$ with, EurobioPlex, RealStar and Bosphore on Elitech showing the lowest CV ($8.6 \pm 3.0 \%$, $9.2 \pm 3.9 \%$ and $10.7 \pm 12.8 \%$, respectively) (Table 4). As expected, an increase in the mean inter-run CV was observed for all assays with the lowest values for AltoStar and RealStar ($9.1 \pm 11.4 \%$ and $15.3 \pm 5.8 \%$, respectively) (Table 4).

3.4. Linearity

Most assays showed an elevated linearity as attested by R^2 values >0.90 (Fig. 2). Superimposable results were obtained when the analysis was repeated including only Panel A samples. In particular, R^2 values >0.90 were observed for 6 out of the 8 commercial assays analyzed and for the home-made assays (Fig. S2).

Conversely, a drop in linearity was observed for HDV-RNA concentrations <1000 IU/ml (Fig. 3). In this setting, only AltoStar, Bosphore on InGenius, RealStar and RoboGene platforms showed an R^2 values >0.80 (Fig. 3).

3.5. Rate of qualitative detection

The rate of qualitative HDV-RNA detection was determined in panel B samples ≤ 1000 IU/ml. The rate of detection was 100 % for concentrations ranging from 1000 to 100 IU/ml for all assays. Conversely, the rate largely varies for concentrations ≤ 40 IU/ml across the assays (Fig. 4). In particular, the AltoStar, Nuclear Laser Medicine and all home-made assays showed a 100 % detection rate for all HDV-RNA concentrations from 40 to 3 IU/ml (Fig. 4). For the RoboGene assay, the detection rate was 100 % for HDV-RNA of 40 and 20 IU/ml, $>75 \%$ for HDV-RNA of 10 and 6 IU/ml and 40 % for HDV-RNA of 3 IU/ml (Fig. 4). Differently, for EurobioPlex, the detection rate showed a progressive drop from 95 % for 40 IU/ml down to 20 % for 3 IU/ml (Fig. 4) while for the remaining assays the detection rate was $<75 \%$ for all HDV-RNA concentrations tested (Fig. 4).

Lastly, among the 383 quantifications of the three negative controls provided, only 1 (0.3 %) was positive with a value of 6.3 IU/ml by

Fig. 1. Accuracy of the assays. The graphs report the accuracy of the HDV-RNA quantification assays. The mean observed value of HDV-RNA of a single center for each expected concentration is reported by a dot and was calculated using the 3 measurements obtained from concentrations of 5.0 and 4.0 \log_{10} IU/ml and the 9 measurements from HDV-RNA concentrations $\leq 3.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml of Panel A. The mean of the values represented by dots is represented by black lines. The reported numbers indicate the mean distances between the mean of all observed HDV-RNA values (black line) and the expected values. The X axis reports expected values in the range between the first tested dilution below LLOQ of each assay and 5.0 \log_{10} IU/ml. For EurobioPlex assay, the HDV-RNA loads <100 IU/ml have not been included because detected values are $<LLOQ$.

RoboGene assay (LoD: 6 IU/ml).

4. Discussion

By involving 30 reference virological centers throughout Italy, this is one of the largest quality control studies that compared the diagnostic performances of 9 assays currently used in clinical practise for HDV-RNA quantification.

Our study showed that the estimated LOD varies across the assays and across the centers using a specific assay, highlighting different degrees of sensitivity and a non-negligible inter-laboratory variability. Inter-Assay variability can be explained by the fact that the assays may have different amplification efficiencies since primers and probe target

different regions of the HDV genome. Conversely, inter-laboratory variability can be related to different factors including slight variations in their protocols, equipment calibration and the methods used for the extraction of nucleic acids. At this regard, different studies have shown that the nucleic acid extraction platform can affect the sensitivity of an assay, thus potentially generating false negative results particularly in samples with low levels of viral nucleic acids [13–16]. This is in keeping with our study in which we have evaluated the impact of the nucleic acid extraction method on the difference between the observed 95 % LOD and the LOD declared by a given assay. We found that for the RoboGene assay, such difference was lower when the manual nucleic acid extraction by RoboScreen INSTANT Virus RNA/DNA Kit was used. Similarly, the extraction platform by ELITech was associated with a

Table 4
Intra- and inter-run reproducibility.

Expected values log ₁₀ IU/ml	RoboGene	EurobioPlex	RealStar	AltoStar ^a	Bosphore	Bosphore on InGenius	Dia.Pro	Nuclear laser medicine	Home- made
Intra-run reproducibility (CV%)									
6.7	12.9 ± 11.4	6.4 ± 4.3	4.9 ± 7.5	-	4.7 ± 1.9	0.3	2.7 ± 0.5	-	12.2 ± 10.1
6.0	12.1 ± 5.9	6.5 ± 5.4	6.9 ± 9.0	-	6.7 ± 5.1	6.7	23.3 ± 15.8	-	13.9 ± 0.5
5.5	9.9 ± 4.2	8.9 ± 3.4	6.3 ± 4.1	-	9.8 ± 8.2	5.9	24.7 ± 14.6	-	8.4 ± 5.9
5.0	11.3 ± 4.1	7.5 ± 5.5	13.0 ± 14.6	-	7.5 ± 3.7	4.5	18.3 ± 4.8	-	6.5 ± 3.2
4.3	12.3 ± 5.9	6.3 ± 5.0	9.2 ± 12.2	-	21.9 ± 5.8	22.5	53.0 ± 10.3	27.0	25.4 ± 1.1
3.7	13.0 ± 8.6	11.6 ± 9.8	12.1 ± 17.6	-	13.6 ± 7.1	6.2	-	10.1	27.7 ± 25.9
3.5	15.0 ± 9.4	5.3 ± 1.7	17.5 ± 22.2	-	19.8 ± 0.8	15.7	-	18.9	11.2 ± 2.1
3.0	17.6 ± 12.1	8.6 ± 6.9	5.7 ± 3.6	-	27.6 ± 15.5	18.7	-	20.8	36.7 ± 36.1
2.6	17.8 ± 10.0	6.5 ± 5.3	9.4 ± 5.2	-	42.4 ± 5.8	0.4	-	15.4	32.9 ± 0.4
2.3	19.9 ± 11.0	11.7 ± 8.2	5.3 ± 5.3	-	12.9 ± 12.6	2.7	-	21.1	30.0 ± 3.0
2.0	32.1 ± 21.5	15.7 ± 7.1	10.6 ± 7.1	-	44.4 ± 17.9	1.1	-	2.8	33.6 ± 23.7
1.6	25.8 ± 19.5	8.3 ± 5.7	-	-	7.3	44.0	-	-	-
Mean ± SD	16.3 ± 6.6	8.6 ± 3.0	9.2 ± 3.9	-	19.2 ± 13.8	10.7 ± 12.8	24.4 ± 18.2	16.6 ± 8.0	21.7 ± 11.3
Inter-run reproducibility (CV%)									
6.7	23.8 ± 25.3	19.9 ± 39.2	21.0 ± 16.3	4.8	29.3 ± 36.1	20.9	27.0 ± 10.6	16.7	62.8 ± 34.8
6.0	29.6 ± 35.6	21.0 ± 31.5	13.8 ± 12.8	-	34.9 ± 25.2	4.4	37.1 ± 3.5	31.3	29.8 ± 1.9
5.5	31.6 ± 35.7	22.6 ± 45.2	15.7 ± 14.3	0.3	28.3 ± 19.5	36.8	24.7 ± 13.5	30.3	27.7 ± 17.6
5.0	28.6 ± 38.5	22.5 ± 57.5	9.3 ± 7.1	0.9	29.4 ± 22.5	14.0	26.3 ± 20.3	30.2	35.4 ± 16.1
4.3	36.8 ± 39.2	15.5 ± 14.4	10.4 ± 15.5	2.5	45.7 ± 56.6	14.8	53.0 ± 16.1	31.9	69.0 ± 55.3
3.7	47.4 ± 36.4	23.8 ± 14.1	19.6 ± 13.4	8.1	19.8 ± 7.1	0.8	-	8.5	49.1 ± 28.6
3.5	42.2 ± 37.2	23.6 ± 21.6	7.3 ± 3.6	10.6	13.6 ± 4.8	37.6	-	0.8	42.4 ± 43.3
3.0	46.4 ± 38.2	15.9 ± 8.0	8.6 ± 5.8	4.2	45.8 ± 34.7	22.3	-	22.1	67.5 ± 22.4
2.6	19.9 ± 14.0	23.5 ± 28.8	19.2 ± 7.0	-	31.6 ± 29.7	66.3	-	22.6	58.8 ± 34.2
2.3	29.9 ± 13.6	23.8 ± 23.9	24.3 ± 25.0	1.3	32.8 ± 13.9	40.7	-	11.9	40.6 ± 1.3
2.0	34.7 ± 15.1	26.5 ± 17.6	19.0 ± 7.0	24.3	28.4 ± 1.8	-	-	31.6	78.2 ± 39.6
1.6	25.5 ± 18.2	43.8 ± 14.6	-	34.4	33.5	-	-	-	-
Mean ± SD	33.0 ± 8.8	23.5 ± 7.2	15.3 ± 5.8	9.1 ± 11.4	30.9 ± 9.5	25.9 ± 19.7	33.6 ± 11.9	21.6 ± 10.8	51.0 ± 17.2

The intra-run and inter-run reproducibility were determined using Panel B samples and expressed as CV%. The CV% was calculated by using the values ranging from LLOQ to 6.7 log₁₀ IU/ml.

^a Intra-run CV has not been calculated for AltoStar since the amount of eluate from nucleic acid extraction was sufficient for only a single quantification (45 µl out of 60 µl of eluted nucleic acid used for RT-PCR, see Table 1).

significantly lower differences between the 95 % LOD and the declared LOD (median difference [IQR]: 0.5 (0.0–3.0 for ELITech extraction method vs 45.5 [4.0–304.6] for the other extraction methods, P-value: 0.023).

Overall data supports the importance to optimize and harmonize the sensitivity of the assays for HDV-RNA quantification. Indeed, a higher sensitivity implies the capability of the assay to detect lower copies of viral genome and in turn lower level of HDV replication. This is critical to reduce the risk to misdiagnose chronic HDV infection. The different sensitivities, observed across the assays, can explain why the rate of chronic HDV infection varies across the different studies [17–19]. Furthermore, as reported by the current guidelines [4], so far, the

scientific community is exploring the possibility to set up a finite course of bulevirtide treatment. In this setting, there is the need of highly sensitive assays that can help identifying patients with an absent/extremely limited production of viral particles that may be candidate to treatment suspension. By using a highly sensitive assay, a recent study has shown that an early achievement and a longer duration of undetectable HDV-RNA during bulevirtide is predictive of sustained HDV undetectability at 1 year after suspending treatment [20]. This supports that HDV-RNA undetectability by a highly sensitive assay could be used as a parameter to guide the suspension of bulevirtide treatment and in turn to identify patients who have achieved a potential HDV cure.

According to the current guidelines [4], the definition of virological

Fig. 2. Linearity of the assays. The graphs report the linear regression of observed vs expected HDV-RNA values (expressed as R^2) for each assay. HDV-RNA values ranging from LLOQ to 6.7 \log_{10} IU/ml (Panel A and B) were analysed for each assay.

response to bulevirtide treatment is a ≥ 2 log HDV-RNA decay or undetectable HDV-RNA during bulevirtide treatment. In this setting other important parameters are the linearity and the accuracy of the assay. The former reflects the capability of a given assay to provide results directly proportional to HDV-RNA concentration present in the peripheral blood while the latter reflects how the assay can correctly quantify the amount of HDV-RNA circulating in peripheral blood. An assay with higher linearity and higher accuracy is critical to properly monitor the decay of HDV-RNA under treatment and thus to properly identify patients who have achieved virological response. Our study showed that 6 out of the 8 commercial assays analyzed and the home-made assays were characterized by an elevated linearity as attested by R^2 values >0.90 . Nevertheless, we noted that some assays underwent a drop in the linearity for HDV-RNA concentrations <1000 IU/ml thus jeopardizing the proper interpretation of virological response. Furthermore, a previous study has shown that patients undergoing HDV-RNA decline <1000 IU/ml during peginterferon alfa-2a treatment are characterized by a milder progression of liver disease even if not achieving undetectable HDV-RNA [21]. On this basis, HDV-RNA <1000 IU/ml has been proposed as cut-off associated with a more benign clinical outcome. This raises the importance of a proper quantification of low level HDV-RNA critical for stratifying patients according to the risk of liver disease

progression.

Overall, our study shows that the diagnostic performance can vary across the different assays and the different participating Centers. This reinforces the recommendation of the current guidelines to monitor HDV-RNA in sequential serum samples in the same laboratory and with the same assay to avoid inter-laboratory and inter-assay variability [4].

Finally, it is important to consider that in our study we analysed samples belonging to genotype 1. Further studies are necessary to systematically evaluate how the genetic backbone of the different genotypes can affect the performances of the assays.

In conclusion, this quality control study underlines a substantial heterogeneity in term of sensitivities across the different assays for HDV-RNA quantification. This heterogeneity is also observed across the different laboratories utilizing each specific assay, highlighting the importance to better harmonize laboratory technical procedures for HDV-RNA quantification.

Furthermore, there is a need to improve the accuracy in the quantification of HDV-RNA particularly at low viral load for most assays.

Overall, these results should be carefully taken into account for the proper monitoring of virological response to anti-HDV drugs and for optimizing therapeutical approaches aimed at setting-up a finite course of anti-HDV treatment.

Fig. 3. Linearity of the assays for HDV-RNA concentrations $< 3 \log_{10}$ IU/ml. The graphs report the linear regression of observed vs expected HDV-RNA values (expressed as R^2) for each assay. HDV-RNA values ranging from LLOQ to $3.0 \log_{10}$ IU/ml (Panel A and B) were analysed for each assay.

Fig. 4. Rate of HDV-RNA qualitative detection. The figure reports the rate of HDV-RNA qualitative detection. The rate of qualitative detection was determined for each assay and for each expected HDV-RNA concentration of panel B ≤ 40 IU/ml. Each column represents a single assay.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

Valentina Svicher: Gilead Sciences. Pietro Lampertico: Gilead Sciences, Altona, Roboscreen. Francesca Ceccherini-Silberstein: Gilead Sciences. Other authors have nothing to disclose.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcv.2025.105850](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcv.2025.105850).

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